

COMPLICATIONS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AND MEASURES TO REDUCE IT

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Abstract: According to current data, 18 million people worldwide suffer from rheumatoid arthritis (RA), which accounts for approximately 0.5–1.0 percent of the world's population. Approximately 70% of patients are women and 55% are people over 55 years of age. It is a systemic process that affects not only the joints, but also various internal organs. In recent years, it has been found that the life expectancy of patients with rheumatoid arthritis decreases by 7-10 years and the risk of developing cardiovascular pathologies increases by 50%. Rheumatoid arthritis is a systemic autoimmune disease, but often affects the arms, wrists, legs, ankles, knees, shoulder and elbow joints. RA is a chronic disease that causes an inflammatory process in the body, mainly in the joints. If left untreated, RA can cause serious damage to joints and surrounding tissues. The disease can cause disorders of the heart, lungs or nervous system.

Key words: erosion, osteoporosis, ankylosis, arthritis, muscle atrophy, tofus, atherosclerosis, myocardial infarction.

Symptoms of RA are chronic joint pain, contracture, feeling of hyperthermia in the joints and their swelling. RA can make it difficult to perform movement and daily activities. In the event of a timely diagnosis, the symptoms of the disease and its development can be controlled with the help of pharmacotherapy, and rehabilitation will help maintain the patient's functionality at an acceptable level. With severe joint injuries, surgical interventions, including joint prostheses, can be used to restore their mobility or reduce pain and maintain performance levels. Rheumatoid arthritis is one of the most common autoimmune diseases, and the immune system does not respond adequately to the body's own tissues and damages them. This chronic systemic connective tissue disease proceeds with major damage to the joints (especially the arms and legs), as well as some manifestations in addition to the joints. They include the formation of erosion and destruction of joints, as well as ankylosis – the combination of articular surfaces with complete immobilization of articulation. In addition, often joint damage is accompanied by problems of various internal organs and systems. Today it is impossible to completely rid a person of the disease. At the same time, almost 20% of patients remain disabled within 5 years after the onset of the disease. However, with the timely onset of treatment, there are ways in which it is possible to significantly reduce the activity of the inflammatory process and achieve a stable remission. The fact that women get sick more often than men, as well as the onset of pregnancy, in most cases is accompanied by the onset of self-remission, which indicates the important importance of hormonal factors. The disease begins with damage to the inner membrane of the immune system, which covers the joint cavity, the membrane swells, the blood supply increases. The shell grows and thickens (such a modified shell is called a pannus). At the same time, Bone Reconstruction is disrupted – the process of destroying old tissues begins to prevail over the process of forming a new one. Erosion forms on the articular surfaces of the bones. The Pannus gradually develops into fibrous tissue, causing articular bone fusion. The main symptom of pathology is pain in the small joints of the legs and arms, which usually appears in the morning and subsides in the evening. Arthritis is symmetrical. Gradually, pathological changes spread to an increasing number of joints (including wrist, knee, leg, jaw, etc.). Inflammation of the joints disrupts its mobility, which is manifested by a gradual increase in morning hardening. Even before the development of arthritis symptoms, non-specific changes such as general weakness and fatigue, muscle pain, temperature, sweating can be noted. As a result of rheumatoid arthritis, muscles, bones, ligaments are damaged. The

appearance of pain and swelling is accompanied by redness and a local increase in temperature in the area of the joint. Muscles gradually atrophy, changes in ligaments lead to the formation of stable contractures—the fingers are hardened in a certain position. The transformation of the synovial membrane and its transformation into a fibrous structure leads to the complete fusion of the articular ends of the bones (ankylosis). The joints of the limbs are gradually deformed and lose the ability to perform their functions. The fingers of the hands turn to the side, bend excessively. Articular joints become irreversible over time. The patient cannot even perform the usual movements (dressing, opening the door, combing hair, holding the glass, etc.). Walking is impaired as a result of inflammation of the knee joints. Especially serious consequences of rheumatoid arthritis are extraarticular and systemic lesions: cardiovascular system (vasculitis, myocarditis, atherosclerosis), skin (formation of rheumatic nodes-tofus), bronchi — pulmonary system (pleurisy, bronchiolitis), nervous system (neuritis, neuropathy), eye (keratoconjunctivitis), kidneys (nephritis, amyloidosis). The mechanism of development can be described as follows: immune cells begin to attack the healthy synovial membrane that surrounds the joint. Gradually, a large number of lymphocytes, monocytes and leukocytes accumulate and swelling occurs. As a result of increased blood flow, an excess of synovial tissue is observed. Osteoclasts are activated, which lead to changes in bone tissue and bone damage. As the disease progresses, the pannus alternates with mature fibrous tissue, causing fusion of the articular surfaces and blocking its mobility. The main symptoms of renal amyloidosis are edema, increased blood pressure, increased protein content in urine analyzes. An accurate diagnosis can be made using a kidney biopsy. Osteonecrosis is a necrosis process that occurs in the bone caused by impaired blood circulation. Symptoms consist in severe pain in the affected joint, movement restriction, the appearance of lameness. Osteoporosis is diagnosed two to three times more often. Ankylosis is a fusion of bones within the joint, often observed in later stages of rheumatoid arthritis. With severe inflammation, cartilage and bone tissue are destroyed, leaving the joint completely immobile. Ankyloses are most characteristic of the joints of the arms and legs. Eye changes in which patients are more likely to be diagnosed with ophthalmic diseases such as cataracts, scleritis, glaucoma, dry eye. As a result, a person's eyelids are difficult to lower, visual acuity decreases, the cornea of the eye becomes cloudy. In complex cases, only a corneal transplant can help. Rheumatoid arthritis can cause serious gastrointestinal bleeding. Rheumatoid arthritis is complicated by gastrointestinal cancer, osteoporosis, Sjögren syndrome, Felty syndrome, lymphoma.

Patients with rheumatoid arthritis are at a relatively high risk of developing cardiovascular disease. Subclinical atherosclerosis occurs in every third patient with rheumatic joint damage. The pathogenesis of atherosclerotic vascular damage is based on systemic inflammation caused by pathological activation of the main branches of congenital and acquired immunity. Typically, endothelial cells and smooth muscle cells ensure the integrity and elasticity of the arterial wall, limiting its infiltration by cells of the immune system. Under the influence of the inflammatory process, these cells are activated and their normal functions are disrupted, which contributes to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. It has been clinically demonstrated that there is a strong correlation between the development of atherosclerosis, rheumatoid inflammatory activity, the development of extra-joint changes, and the overabundance of anti-inflammatory mediators and autoantibodies. In this regard, the study of the effect of antibodies on the cyclic citrulline-containing peptide is of particular interest, its increased production in rheumatoid arthritis is associated with the synthesis of anti-inflammatory and prothrombotic mediators, an increase in the thickness of the intima-media complex of sleep arteries and a high risk of cardiovascular death. It should be noted that part of the immune biomarkers are detected in the blood of patients with rheumatoid arthritis long before the clinical picture of the disease, which indicates the development of subclinical inflammation of the joints, as well as an increased risk of cardiovascular complications. Scientific research shows that patients with rheumatoid arthritis have a 50% higher risk of dying from cardiovascular disease. In rheumatoid arthritis, heart damage can develop in two ways. The first is that damage to the coronary vessels occurs with the formation of coronary heart disease. Characteristic features of atherosclerosis, which develops in rheumatoid arthritis, include damage to the coronary arteries, premature recurrence of acute coronary syndrome, increased mortality after the first myocardial infarction, and a high incidence of its

asymptomatic appearance. In the latter, with the development of cardiomyopathy, changes in the cell composition and structure of the heart muscle are observed, which are usually manifested by hypertrophy of the ventricular myocardium and an increase in the volume of the heart chambers. Cardiomyopathy is dangerous due to its high cardiovascular mortality due to progressive heart failure. Some patients may develop brown heart muscle atrophy, which is accompanied by the accumulation of lipid or glycoprotein pigment lipofuscin in cardiomyocytes. These changes can lead to the development of pain. In most patients with rheumatoid arthritis, against the background of the manifestation of changes in the joints, the symptoms of damage to the coronary arteries and heart muscle do not care, but systemic manifestations of rheumatoid arthritis, including heart damage, determine the prognosis of the disease, so it is very important to detect and treat them early, especially modern diagnostic methods allow you to In rheumatoid arthritis, the most common are the symptoms of heart and vascular damage, which are chest discomfort, which are weakly manifested in nature, do not have pronounced localization and usually do not stop with nitrates. In addition, patients may complain of irregular heartbeat, signs of heart failure, sometimes shortness of breath during exercise. When examining patients with moderate to high activity of rheumatoid arthritis, symptoms of increased blood pressure, decreased heart rate variability, left ventricular hypertrophy may be observed. With auscultation of the heart, tachycardia, cardiac arrhythmias, weakening of the first Tone with systolic noise can be detected, often a tone III can be heard. Given the main role of chronic inflammation in the development of atherosclerosis as a result of rheumatoid arthritis, effective anti-inflammatory therapy is important in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. Treatment is carried out using the European Association of rheumatologists treatment methods. In this case, the main goal of therapy is to achieve clinical remission or low disease activity, to closely monitor the patient using proven complex indicators (every 1-3 months), strictly controlling the changes. Symptomatic therapy is aimed at reducing inflammation and pain, and includes taking medications, including in the form of injections (drug blockade, topical injection therapy). The main component of the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis is basic therapy, the task of which is to suppress the activity of the autoimmune process. In addition, if necessary, effective methods of restoring the structure and functions of joints can be used, such as plasma therapy, bioimplant treatment, exercise therapy, etc. Thus, the treatment consists in focusing on maintaining the patient's quality of life indicators and social activity, carefully monitoring the treatment process, extensive use of genetically engineered biological drugs, maintaining the achieved effect and ensuring the patient's active participation in the treatment process. At the initial stage of RA, severe functional disturbances and extraarticular disturbances are not observed—so there is a high probability of reverting tissue changes to their state. Therefore, early initiation of rehabilitation measures is also effective in preventing and reducing disability. The rehabilitation program RA should be based on the individual characteristics of the patient. It consists of various complex activities (aerobics, gymnastics, yoga), physiotherapy (laser therapy, cryotherapy, electrotherapy, balneotherapy), occupational therapy, psychotherapy. Promoting the effective use of antirheumatic and biological drugs in patients with rheumatoid arthritis, reduces the symptoms of the disease in patients, reduces joint deformities, long remission of the disease is observed, and the patient's quality of life is improved. Treatment of this disease in patients consists not only in eliminating the symptom of pain, but also in promoting the development of the disease process by explaining that it can be stopped by the use of antirheumatic drugs.

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